

APPLICATIONS OF ARGOS AND RAMS MEASUREMENTS
IN EQUATORIAL PACIFIC OCEAN-ATMOSPHERE INTERACTION STUDIES

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Abstract

The ARGOS (and before its launch in October 1978 the RAMS) data acquisition system is (was) used routinely on surface moorings instrumented with oceanographic and meteorological recorders. On one occasion during 1983 when extremely strong currents moved a mooring 31 km from its original position, ARGOS location measurements probably meant the difference between recovery and non-recovery; a similar situation also occurred in 1977 when RAMS was routinely used to locate our surface buoys. In addition to buoy position information, our experience with telemetering time-averaged wind velocity components and air and sea surface temperatures via ARGOS will be described. The requirement for real-time acquisition of meteorological and oceanographic data throughout the equatorial Pacific will be discussed.

1. Introduction

An important aspect of NOAA's Equatorial Pacific Ocean Climate Studies (EPOCS) program is to understand (and ultimately to predict) the role of the tropical Pacific Ocean in influencing the long-term behavior of the global atmosphere. Episodes of anomalously warm water in the equatorial Pacific may be associated with abnormal weather over the mid-latitude regions of the Northern Hemisphere, e.g., lower atmospheric pressure in the Aleutian Low and large perturbations in the seasonal position of the Jet Stream (Rasmusson and Wallace, 1983). Two immediate objectives of EPOCS are to understand the important processes which generate, maintain and dissipate the large-scale interannual sea surface temperature (SST) variations centered along the equator in the eastern and central Pacific, and to improve quasi-real-time model predictions of SST behavior. Because the velocity field within $1-2^\circ$ of the equator is not geostrophic, moored current measurements are required in the upper ocean to unravel the complex dynamical processes (e.g., Kelvin and Rossby waves; wind-generated mixing; zonal, meridional and vertical advection; undercurrent meandering; air-sea heat and moisture fluxes) influencing SST.

When our first prototype equatorial surface mooring (EQUA-1) was deployed in August 1976 at 0° , 150°W , knowledge of the magnitudes of the variations of the upper ocean current and temper-

ature fields was extremely limited. Knauss' (1960) very limited observations made in May 1958 by lowering a current meter from a ship at 14 sites along the equator from $100-140^\circ\text{W}$ showed a thin (~ 20 m) westward flowing South Equatorial Current with speeds of $\sim 0.1 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ occurring above an ~ 200 m thick eastward flowing undercurrent with maximum speeds ($1.25 - 1.5 \text{ m s}^{-1}$) at the equator; below the undercurrent the flow determined by floats was westward ($\sim 0.1 \text{ m s}^{-1}$) to 1000 m depth.

Not only do the large SST anomalies associated with El Niño episodes occur in a data sparse region due to the virtual absence of ships, but the large currents in the core of the undercurrent and the strong shears within the uppermost 200-300 m create a harsh environment for surface moorings. Prior to our EQUA-1 measurements, the longest time series observations made within the undercurrent were 13 days in the Atlantic (Stalcup and Metcalf, 1966) and 25 days in the Pacific (Taft et al., 1974); time series of currents in the mixed layer along the Pacific equator were unknown. Because of the relatively weak, steady tradewinds, we presumed the speed of the westward flowing South Equatorial Current to be small ($\sim 0.1 \text{ m s}^{-1}$) and time-independent. One of our discoveries has been the documentation of near-surface (15-20 m depth), eastward currents of $1.0-1.5 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ (Halpern, 1983). Another discovery is the annual occurrence of a Kelvin wave each Northern Hemisphere spring (e.g., April) when the transport (or depth-averaged current) in the equatorial undercurrent doubles (Knox and Halpern, 1982; Hayes and Halpern, 1984). These current perturbations produce a tremendous increase in current drag on the upper portion of the mooring where virtually all our instrumentation is placed.

Fortunately our first equatorial mooring (EQUA-1) survived its brief 35-day deployment at 0° , 150°W . With experience and confidence gained from our EQUA-1 mooring, which contained only a wind recorder and 2 current meters, we deployed an instrumented mooring (EQUA-2) at 0° , 125°W for nearly 100 days. Only because of the Nimbus 6 RAMS position data was this buoy recovered.

2. Instrumentation

On 12 June 1975 the NASA Nimbus 6 meteorological satellite was launched with a random access measurement system (RAMS) onboard which

allowed fixed and mobile platforms to randomly transmit signals to the polar-orbiting satellite, thus eliminating satellite interrogation. A specific location on the Earth was viewed twice every 24-h period, once in sunlight and once in darkness. As the Nimbus 6 spacecraft passed over the various platforms on or near Earth, RAMS detected and acquired the incoming platform transmissions, distinguished the platforms by identification codes, and determined the location of the transmitter platform by the Doppler shift method.

The Nimbus 6 RAMS technique signaled the commencement of an engineering program at NOAA's Pacific Marine Environmental Laboratory (PMEL) to increase the reliability of our surface moorings which are difficult to maintain on-station in the harsh environment of the upper ocean but which, nonetheless, are necessary for ocean-atmosphere interaction studies because time series observations of winds and near-surface currents and temperatures must be made (e.g., Halpern, 1974). Because the reliability of surface moorings is about one-half compared to subsurface moorings (Walden and Panicker, 1973), RAMS provided a unique opportunity to continually monitor the location of the buoy and compare the measured excursions with those computed from a model (Milburn, 1979), enabling a validation of the mooring design. Beginning in August 1975 all our moored surface buoys were equipped with a buoy transmit terminal (BTT, used with RAMS) until 1980 when a platform transmit terminal (PTT, used with ARGOS) was used.

In October 1978 the first ARGOS satellite-based location and data collection system was launched on a Tiros N satellite of the NOAA satellite series and subsequently on other NOAA polar-orbiting environmental satellites. A PTT mounted on the surface buoy provides an up-link transmission between the mooring and satellite without the need for satellite interrogation. A PTT transmits location data every 40-60 seconds and ARGOS receives these messages on a random access basis. The buoy location is determined by the Doppler effect; rms accuracy is ~0.3 km and 5-6 locations can be made every 24 h at the equator (WMO, 1983).

The ARGOS-PTT system of buoy location has been used on 34 moorings in the eastern and central Pacific since August 1980 (Freitag et al., 1984). Reliable data were obtained on all but five occasions. The five malfunctions were

Figure 1. A segment of the Nimbus 5 RAMS position data of the EQUA-2 mooring.

Figure 2. Downward tension (pounds; 1 lb = 0.454 kg) at the surface buoy.

caused by incorrectly entering the hexadecimal code and by improper assembly of the sea surface temperature probe which drained the battery.

3. Observations and Results

3.1 EQUA-2, April-July 1977

This surface mooring contained a wind recorder, a RAMS buoy transmit terminal, current meters at 10, 50, 100, 150 and 200 m, a thermistor chain with 17 thermistors, tension recorders at 4 and 275 m, and other equipment. The effective diameter of the uppermost 275 m of the mooring line was exceedingly large (~5 cm); fairing was used to reduce current drag. Deployment occurred on 4 April 1977. Water depth was nearly 4660 m. From 5-13 April the buoy position was relatively constant (Figure 1). Between 13 and 18 April the mooring moved approximately 16 km eastward of its original position (Figure 1). The water depth at its new position was about 4495 m, approximately 165 m shallower; the anchor did not move again throughout the remainder of the deployment. The downward tension at the buoy was 3300-3400 lb (Figure 2) which was about 1100 lb greater than the amount assumed in our mooring design. The extremely

Figure 3. Three-day vector-averages of the eastward current component at 50, 100, 150 and 200 m depths at EQUA-2 (~0°, 125°W).

large eastward currents (Figure 3), especially at 50 m depth where 2.0 m s^{-1} speeds were recorded for several days, increased the drag to such an extent that the buoy "walked" eastward to a shallower site. This being our first springtime equatorial mooring we were not aware of the large currents associated with the annual Kelvin wave. Without knowledge of the buoy's new location, it is doubtful whether the mooring would have been recovered because of the limited shiptime available for a comprehensive search and because the search would probably have been made west of the deployment position assuming westward motion induced by the prevailing tradewinds and South Equatorial Current. This was our second equatorial mooring and our first multi-month mooring with sufficient instrumentation for equatorial air-sea interaction studies; had it been lost, it is questionable whether our embryonic equatorial moored measurement project would have grown.

3.2 T32, April-October 1983

This surface mooring contained a wind recorder, ARGOS platform transmit terminal, and current meters at 15, 50 and 100 m depths. It was deployed on April 1983 at $00^{\circ}02'N$, $108^{\circ}00'W$ in water 3651 m deep. Between 10 and 15 May, the mooring moved eastward by nearly 31 km (Figure 4); water depth at its new position was ~ 100 m deeper. The mooring displacement was caused by increased current drag. Unusually large eastward currents, which were greater than 1.75 m s^{-1} at 15 m (Figure 5) and 1.5 m s^{-1} at 50 m, had been produced by the extremely anomalous occurrence of eastward winds in the eastern Pacific during the spectacular 1982-83 El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO) event; the maximum sea surface temperature in the eastern equatorial Pacific had occurred in May.

Another surface mooring nearly identical to T32 but containing current meters at 15, 50, 75, 100, 150, 200 and 250 m depths was located at 0° , $109^{\circ}W$, i.e., approximately 100 km west of T32. Using the $109^{\circ}W$ current profile, the computed T32 buoy watch-circle radius was 2.5 km and the T32 surface tension was 3000 lb, which was about 900 lb (or 43%) greater than normal. While the large currents encountered in May 1983 seemed to be the primary mechanism generating the onset of motion of the T32 mooring, these same currents did not move the adjacent mooring at $109^{\circ}W$ where the current drag was greater because of the increased amount of instrumentation. The dynamics of the onset of motion of a surface mooring is complex and is determined by many factors, such as the slope of the bottom, the type of sediments and holding-power of the anchor, the precise scope of the mooring line, and the currents.

3.3 T32 ARGOS Meteorological Platform

The T32 equatorial mooring at $\sim 0^{\circ}$, $108^{\circ}W$ contained a prototype ARGOS meteorological platform (AMP) constructed by PMEL's Engineering Division. Vector-averaged Cartesian wind com-

Figure 4. A segment of the Tiros N ARGOS position data of the T32 mooring.

ponents and scalar-averaged air and sea surface temperatures were measured; eventually the AMP will also be used to measure and transmit atmospheric pressure, humidity, and ocean current measurements.

Wind speed is sampled continuously and wind direction relative to magnetic north is measured with a balanced wind vane and a flux-gate compass placed inside the instrument. Vector wind components are computed at 0.5 s intervals and 2-h averages are stored on a magnetic tape cassette and also in a buffer. Temperatures at 1 m depth (which we call sea surface temperature) and 3.0 m height are measured at 8 s intervals with thermistors and 2-h averages are recorded on tape

Figure 5. (A) Low-pass filtered (31-day running mean) and (B) daily averages of the zonal current (positive is eastward) at 15 m at $\sim 0^{\circ}$, $109^{\circ}30'W$. Time scales are different in (A) and (B). The current speeds in May 1983 were anomalously large compared to other times in the April 1980 - October 1983 period.

cassette and also stored in a buffer. The data transmitted to ARGOS on each satellite overflight consists of four consecutive 2-h averages of the wind and temperature measurements. Every 2 h new data replaces the data entered into the buffer 8 h earlier.

The AMP recorded and transmitted winds and SST from the 24 April 1983 deployment until about 1 July (winds) and 10 July (SST), presumably because of destruction of the wind sensors by an intruder and subsequent power drain of the battery. (Upon recovery of this mooring in October 1983, two tag-lines were tied to the surface buoy and fishing net was found on the mooring line.) The mooring at 0°, 109°W contained our standard vector-averaging wind recorder (VAWR), which normally yields 100% reliable data but on this occasion malfunctioned soon after deployment. Because the AMP wind directions are questionable and the radiation shield was damaged during deployment, only wind speeds and sea surface temperatures are compared. The good correlation (and at times excellent agreement) found between the wind speeds (Figure 6A) and the excellent agreement between the sea surface temperature data (Figure 6B) for the initial 2-week period was extremely encouraging. The cause of the 1.5-2.0°C difference in SST from 15 to 19 May is unknown. A more robust AMP (model 1A) was deployed at 0°, 108°W in April 1984; its performance remains to be evaluated.

4. Concluding Remarks

The RAMS and ARGOS location system is extremely beneficial for surface moorings instrumented with oceanographic and meteorological recorders because if a mooring drifts off-station and is not recovered there is considerable loss of costly equipment and invaluable data, and the drifting buoy may present a hazard to navigation.

Satellite-based real time data collection systems (e.g., ARGOS) are reliable and provide an opportunity to assimilate time series of surface

Figure 6. Intercomparisons of (A) wind speeds recorded with a VAWR at 0°, 109°W (dashed line) and an AMP at 0°, 108°W (solid line) and (B) sea surface temperature measurements recorded with a VAWR at 0°, 109°W (dashed line) and an AMP at 0°, 108°W (solid line).

meteorological and upper ocean measurements into computer models forecasting the behavior of the ocean's temperature and current fields. The accuracy, timeliness and general utility of projections of large-scale phenomena, such as El Niño, are limited by scarcity of observations, especially in the central and eastern equatorial Pacific, for initialization and verification of the models. While a substantial amount of work remains to be done in merging data and models and for improving our understanding of the response of the ocean to atmospheric forcing, we are developing a capability of an El Niño detection system. Real time data acquisition from instrumented surface moorings positioned throughout the data-sparse region of the central equatorial Pacific from about 160°E to 110°W will monitor the generation in the western Pacific and ensuing eastward movement of the characteristic El Niño anomalies in the surface wind, sea surface temperature, and upper ocean current and thermal fields. In the onset phase of El Niño, near-surface currents reverse direction from westward to eastward, the zonal slope of the thermocline decreases, the mixed layer thickness increases, upper ocean heat content rises, sea surface temperature increases, and the westward winds decrease in speed and even become eastward (Halpern, 1983); these dramatic changes occur along the equator. Satellite data relay systems will form an integral portion of the monitoring network to record future El Niño events which occur at irregular intervals every three to seven years.

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